

SYNTHESES IN THE ACRIDINE SERIES. PART VII*. N-SUBSTITUTED
3-METHOXY-7-CHLORO-9-AMINOACRIDINES

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Eighteen N-substituted 3-methoxy-7-chloro-9-aminoacridines have been synthesised in order to study their antimalarial properties.

In continuation with the work on the synthesis of 9-dialkylamino-alkylamino-acridines, carrying a methoxyl group and a chlorine atom on either nuclei, we have now prepared a number of 3-methoxy-7-chloro-9-(dialkylamino-alkyl)aminoacridines. It is interesting to note that the relative position of the chlorine atom and the methoxyl group in these compounds is the same as in the atebirin molecule.

The parent 3-methoxy-7 : 9 dichloroacridine (VI) was obtained by the treatment of 4'-chlorodiphenylamine-5-methoxy-2-carboxylic acid (III) with excess phosphoryl chloride. This diphenylamine acid (III) in turn could be obtained by either of the two methods: (a) The Ullman condensation between 2-chloro-4-methoxybenzoic acid and *p*-chloroaniline or (b) the Jaminson and Turner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1954) extension of the Chapman rearrangement (*ibid.*, 1929, 569) of properly substituted benziminophenyl ether to the diphenylamine derivative.

Thus, methyl 4-methoxysalicylate on condensation with *N-p*-chlorophenylbenziminocloride (obtained by the treatment of *p*-chlorobenzanilide with phosphorus pentachloride) gave *N-p*-chlorophenylbenziminoc-5'-methoxy-2'-carbomethoxyphenyl ether (I). When (I) was heated at 270° an exothermic reaction took place and methyl *N*-benzoyl-4'-chloro-5-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylate (II) was obtained in 80% yield. Partial hydrolysis of (II) with one equivalent of aqueous alcoholic potassium hydroxide gave *N*-benzoyl-4'-chloro-5-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid (IV), while treatment with excess of alkali resulted in the formation of the required 4'-chlorodiphenylamine-5-methoxy-2-carboxylic acid (III). This latter method for the preparation of (III) is to be very much preferred to the Ullman synthesis as it involves the use of the readily accessible methyl 4-methoxysalicylate as compared to the more difficultly obtainable 2-chloro-4-methoxybenzoic acid used in the Ullman condensation. When the partially hydrolysed compound (IV) was heated to 270°, 3-methoxy-7-chloroacridone (V) was obtained with the elimination of benzoic acid. Similarly when either of the compounds (I) or (II) was heated to 320°, elements of methyl benzoate were lost and 3-methoxy-7-chloroacridone (V) could be isolated. This on

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reaction with excess of phosphoryl chloride was converted into 3-methoxy-7:9-dichloroacridine (VI). The various reactions are summarised as above.

The Chapman rearrangement very probably consists in the nucleophilic displacement by the pair of electrons of the nitrogen atom on the carbon atom of the benzene ring attached to the oxygen atom, resulting in the attachment of the phenyl group to the nitrogen atom and rupture of the phenyl-oxygen linkage as shown below.

Such a view is in accord with the observation of Chapman (*loc. cit.*) according to which the rearrangement is facilitated when the benzene ring attached to the nitrogen atom carries electropositive substituents like methoxyl group etc. in the *ortho* or *para* position to the nitrogen atom and the phenyl ether portion of the molecule carries electronegative substituents like nitro group etc. in the *ortho* or *para* position to the oxygen atom. The former results in the increased electron density at the nitrogen atom, while the latter gives rise to an electron deficient center at the site of attack. Both these effects make it possible for the rearrangement to be carried at a comparatively low temperature.

EXPERIMENTAL

Methyl 4-methoxysalicylate was obtained by the methylation of β -resorcylic acid, which was prepared according to the directions given in the "Organic Synthesis" (Vol. X, p. 94). Gomberg and Johnson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 1687) claim to have prepared ethyl 4-methoxysalicylate by esterification of 4-methoxysalicylic acid by the use of dry hydrogen chloride in absolute alcohol. This observation, however, could not be repeated and 4-methoxysalicylic acid separated out almost completely from ethyl alcohol or methyl alcohol saturated with hydrogen chloride. When concentrated sulphuric acid was used in place of dry hydrogen chloride and the reaction mixture was refluxed for about 4 hours, a 30% yield of the ester was obtained.

When 4-methoxysalicylic acid was treated with thionyl chloride in absolute benzene and the resultant acid chloride was further reacted with absolute methyl alcohol, 33% yield of the ester was obtained. This procedure was, however, complicated by the formation of considerable amount of a polymer in the reaction. After considerable experience treatment of β -resorcylic acid in alkaline solution with excess of dimethyl sulphate was found to give very satisfactory results and led to the formation of the desired methyl 4-methoxysalicylate directly without the isolation of the intermediate 4-methoxysalicylic acid. β -Resorcylic acid (77 g.) was dissolved in 320 c.c. of water containing 40 g. of sodium hydroxide. Freshly distilled dimethyl sulphate (240 c.c.) was added and the mixture shaken vigorously for one hour. About 50 g. of sodium bicarbonate was added and the reaction mixture set aside

for 24 hours. It was ensured that the reaction mixture was alkaline. The ester which separated as a heavy brown oil was removed by extraction with chloroform. After distilling off the solvent, the ester was distilled in vacuum, b. p. $134^{\circ}/7$ mm., yield 80%. On seeding, the entire product set to a white crystalline mass. It has a very characteristic odour of oil of anise.

N-p-Chlorophenylbenzimidino-5'-methoxy-2'-carbomethoxyphenyl Ether (I).—Clean sodium metal (5 g., 0.217 mol.) was dissolved in 250 c.c. of absolute alcohol. To the cooled solution, methyl 4-methoxysalicylate (40 g., 0.217 mol.) was added rapidly, followed immediately by a solution of *N-p*-chlorophenylbenzimidino chloride (50 g., 0.197 mol.) dissolved in about 100 c.c. of dry ether. There was a considerable generation of heat and the reaction mixture became cloudy at once. It was vigorously shaken for a few minutes and then allowed to stand overnight. During this time, considerable quantity of *N-p*-chlorophenylbenzimidino-5'-methoxy-2'-carbomethoxyphenyl ether had crystallised out. A greater portion of the solvent was distilled off and the residue diluted with water. The precipitated mass was filtered off and recrystallised from ethanol as white prisms, m.p. $125-26^{\circ}$, yield 83%. (Found: N, 3.64. $C_{22}H_{18}O_4NCl$ requires N, 3.54 per cent).

The corresponding carboethoxy derivative was obtained similarly by using ethyl 4-methoxysalicylate and was crystallised from absolute alcohol as white prisms, m.p. $104-105^{\circ}$.

Methyl N-Benzoyl-4'-chloro-5-methoxydiphenylamine-2'-carboxylate (II).—*N-p*-Chlorophenylbenzimidino-5'-methoxy-2'-carbomethoxyphenyl ether (20 g.) was heated in a wide-mouthed pyrex tube to 270° , at which temperature the isomerisation began and the temperature rapidly rose to 310° . When the temperature began to fall heating was discontinued. On cooling, the product solidified to a glassy mass. After three crystallisations from absolute alcohol, it was obtained as white glistening clusters, m.p. $119-21^{\circ}$, yield 80%. (Found: N, 3.60. $C_{22}H_{18}O_4NCl$ requires N, 3.54 per cent). For the subsequent step, the crude product could be used without purification.

4'-Chlorodiphenylamine-5-methoxy-2-carboxylic Acid (III).—Methyl-*N*-benzoyl-4'-chloro-5-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylate (20 g.) was dissolved in about 250 c.c. of 95% ethyl alcohol and more than 4 equivalents of sodium hydroxide (10 g.), dissolved in about 40 c.c. of water, was added to this solution. The mixture was heated under a gentle reflux and a clear solution resulted after about 30 minutes. Refluxing was continued for another 2 hours. The reaction mixture was diluted with 300 c.c. of water, and alcohol was distilled off. The residue on acidification with hydrochloric acid gave a mixture of benzoic acid and 4'-chlorodiphenylamine-5-methoxy-2-carboxylic acid. This was filtered off and benzoic acid was removed by washing with hot water. The diphenylamine acid was crystallised from 95% alcohol as pale needles, m.p. $181-82^{\circ}$, yield 77%. (Found: N, 5.19. $C_{14}H_{12}O_3NCl$ requires N, 5.04 per cent). The same acid was also obtained in 30-40% yield by the Ullman condensation of 2-chloro-4-methoxybenzoic acid and *p*-chloroaniline by the procedure described in earlier papers.

4'-Chlorodiphenylamine-5-methoxy-2-carboxyl chloride was prepared in the usual way by the treatment of the diphenylamine acid with phosphorus pentachloride

in absolute petroleum ether. It was crystallised from light petroleum ether as yellow needles. (Found: N, 4.62. $C_{14}H_{12}O_2$, NCl_2 requires N; 4.74 per cent). The product was found to explode with evolution of hydrogen chloride at 118° and got converted into the acridone which did not melt up to 300° . Drozdov (*J. Gen. Chem. U.S.S.R.*, 1935, 8, 937) also observed that some diphenylamine acid chlorides, when heated at temperatures above their melting points, were transformed into acridones.

3-Methoxy-7:9-dichloroacridine (VI) was obtained by the treatment of 4'-chlorodiphenylamine-5-methoxy-2-carboxylic acid with excess of phosphoryl chloride. It was crystallised from absolute benzene as yellow needles, m.p. $194-95^\circ$, yield 80%. (Found: N, 5.15. $C_{14}H_9ONCl_2$ requires N, 5.03 per cent).

N-Benzoyl-4'-chloro-5-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic Acid.—Sodium metal (1.25 g.) was dissolved in 200 c.c. of 97% ethanol and methyl *N*-benzoyl-4'-chloro-5-methoxy-2-carboxylate (1 equiv., 21 g.) was added to the solution. The mixture was refluxed for about 2 hours; 300 c.c. of water was added and the alcohol was distilled off. The solution on acidification with hydrochloric acid gave an oil which solidified after trituration. This was filtered and extracted with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and filtered free of any insoluble impurities. The sodium salt was cautiously neutralised with hydrochloric acid and the white precipitated mass was collected. After drying it was crystallised from benzene. A second crystallisation from a mixture of acetone-petroleum ether (b.p. $40^\circ-60^\circ$) gave the acid in white needles, m.p. $104-106^\circ$. (Found: N, 3.84. $C_{21}H_{16}O_4NCl$ requires N, 3.77 per cent).

3-Methoxy-7-chloroacridone (V) was obtained according to the following three methods:

(a) Hydrolysis of 3-methoxy-7:9-dichloroacridine by refluxing with 5% hydrochloric acid for about 4 hours.

(b) *N*-benzoyl-4'-chloro-5-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid was heated at 270° for five minutes when benzoic acid sublimed off. The product was washed with boiling water to remove benzoic acid and the residual acridone was crystallised from glacial acetic acid as a white mass which did not melt till 310° .

(c) By heating methyl *N*-benzoyl-4'-chloro-5-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylate (or) *N*-*p*-chlorophenylbenzimidazo-5-methoxy-2-carbomethoxyphenyl ether at 320° for 5 minutes, when methyl benzoate distilled off. Steam was passed into the residual mass in order to remove the last traces of methyl benzoate. Acridone was filtered off and crystallised from glacial acetic acid. (Found: N, 5.23. $C_{14}H_{10}O_2NCl$ requires N, 5.39 per cent).

3-Methoxy-7-chloroacridone on treatment with excess of phosphoryl chloride in the usual way gave 3-methoxy-7:9-dichloroacridine (VI).

3-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(dialkylamino-alkyl)aminoacridines.—The condensation of 3-methoxy-7:9-dichloroacridine with various amines was carried out in phenol according to the conditions described in earlier papers. The condensation products in some cases were separated from any acridone, also formed by hydrolysis, by dissolution in dilute acetic acid. The condensation products, thus obtained, were characterised either as the free bases, or their hydrochlorides or meconates. The hydrochlorides usually crystallised from absolute ethanol or ethanol-ether mixture. The various compounds

prepared* are listed in Table I below. 3-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-aminoacridine was prepared by treatment of 3-methoxy-7:9-dichloroacridine with ammonium carbonate in phenolic solution and was further condensed with *p*-acetylamino benzenesulphony chloride.

TABLE I

N-Substituted-3-methoxy-7-chloro-9-aminoacridines.

o Substituent-R.	M.p. of base, hydrochloride or meconate.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
			Calc.	Found.
1. Amino-	248-50°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Cl	10.83	10.50
2. Phenylamino-	200-201°	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ ON ₂ Cl	8.37	8.12
3. 4'-Methoxyphenylamino-	243-44°	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ (O) ₂ N ₂ Cl.HCl	6.98	6.84
4. Carboxymethylamino-	240-41°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	8.84	9.06
5. 4'-Acetylamino-phenyl- sulphonylamino-	Above 300°.	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₂ ClS	9.22	9.35
6. 4'-Sulphonylamino- phenylamino-	261-63°	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ ClS	10.15	10.20
7. -HN(CH ₂) ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	186-87°	C ₂₁ H ₂₈ ON ₃ Cl.2HCl	9.44	9.97
8. -HN(CH ₂) ₂ N(<i>n</i> -propyl) ₂	198-99°	C ₂₃ H ₃₀ ON ₃ Cl.2HCl	8.88	9.12
9. -HN(CH ₂) ₂ N(<i>n</i> -butyl) ₂	152-54°	C ₂₅ H ₃₄ ON ₃ Cl.2HCl	8.39	8.45
10. -HN(CH ₂) ₂ N(<i>n</i> -amyl) ₂ ^a	248° (d)	C ₂₇ H ₃₈ ON ₃ Cl.2HCl	7.92	7.73
11. -HN(CH ₂) ₂ N-Ph	264° (d)	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ ON ₃ Cl.2HCl	9.20	9.31
12. -HN(CH ₂) ₂ N(C ₂ N ₅) ₂ ^a	210°	C ₂₇ H ₃₈ ON ₃ Cl.2HCl	9.16	9.34
13. -HN(CH ₂) ₂ N(<i>n</i> -propyl) ₂	216-17°	C ₂₄ H ₃₂ ON ₃ Cl.2HCl	8.72	8.91
14. -HN(CH ₂) ₂ N(<i>n</i> -butyl) ₂ ^a	168-69° (d)	C ₂₆ H ₃₆ ON ₃ Cl.2HCl	7.11	6.80
15. -HN(CH ₂) ₂ N(<i>isobutyl</i>) ₂ ^a	159° (d)	C ₂₆ H ₃₆ ON ₃ Cl.2HCl	7.12	6.78
16. -HN(CH ₂) ₂ N(<i>n</i> -amyl) ₂ ^b	112°	C ₂₇ H ₃₈ ON ₃ Cl.C ₇ H ₄ O ₇	6.38	5.46
17. -HN(CH ₂) ₂ N-Ph	243-45°	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ ON ₃ Cl.2HCl	8.93	9.25
18. -HN(CH ₂) ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	222-24°	C ₂₃ H ₃₀ ON ₃ Cl.2HCl	8.57	8.63

- (a) The hydrochloride forms a stable hydrate. Combustion results are given for the anhydrous compounds.
- (b) The meconate seemed to form a very stable hydrate which could not be made anhydrous even after long drying over phosphorus pentoxide under high vacuum.